

Essentials of recurrent aphthous stomatitis (canker sores): A mini-review

Now published in Biomedical Reports doi: <https://doi.org/10.3892/br.2019.1221>

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Keywords: aphthae, etiology, pathogenesis, experimental models, therapeutics, review

ABSTRACT

Recurrent aphthous stomatitis (also known as canker sores) is the most common disease of the oral mucosa. Unlike with caries or periodontal disease, patients who suffer from it can do nothing to prevent it. The clinical picture of recurrent aphthous stomatitis is characterized by recurrent episodes of solitary or multiple painful ulcerations without association with systemic diseases. The objective of this narrative review is to present the essential characteristics of recurrent aphthous stomatitis, including its definition, pathogenesis, clinical and microscopic characteristics, proposed experimental models and recommended pharmacological management. This text can serve as a theoretical framework for research proposals.

INTRODUCTION

Recurrent aphthous stomatitis (RAS, also known as canker sores) is the most common disease of the oral mucosa (1). This paper presents key aspects of RAS, integrating clinical, histological and molecular concepts that every medical professional who faces this disease must know.

DEFINITION

The clinical picture of RAS is characterized by recurrent episodes of solitary or multiple painful ulcerations (2) without association with systemic diseases (3). The latter is relevant since RAS should not be confused with aphthous ulcerations.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Aphthous ulcerations (or RAS-like ulcerations) have an underlying systemic cause, so they should be considered a distinct medical condition (3). Differential diagnoses should be established with autoinflammatory syndromes (e.g., periodic fever with adenitis, pharyngitis, and aphthae [PFAPA syndrome]; Behcet syndrome; Crohn's disease), and immunodeficiency states (e.g., nutritional defects such as in celiac disease and other gastrointestinal disorders, immune defects such as HIV/AIDS, or neutrophil defects such as cyclic neutropenia) (4). The term RAS should be used for ulceration seen in the absence of systemic disease.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

RAS affects approximately 20% of the general population (5), with an incidence ranging from 5% to 60% in different groups studied (6, 7). Its onset seems to peak between 10 and 19 years of age (8) and interestingly, its frequency decreases with advancing age (9).

PATHOGENESIS

The etiology and pathogenesis of RAS remain unclear. Multiple factors are associated with the establishment of this disease, including a positive family history, food hypersensitivity, smoking cessation, psychological stress, and immune disturbance (8, 10). Although for this evidence, there is often an absence of statistical risk analysis. An immune dysregulation linked to several triggers may facilitate the development of RAS. The role of the immune system and inflammatory processes have been confirmed in recent large-scale bioinformatics analyses (11, 12). It is known that a Th1-type hyperimmune response favors the appearance of inflammatory reactions that precede ulcerations (Figure 1) (13, 14).

Figure 1. Cell-mediated immunity in pathogenesis of recurrent aphthous stomatitis.

Lymphocytic cells infiltrate the oral epithelium and edema develops as a result of inflammatory stimuli. Keratinocyte vacuolization and localized vasculitis cause a papular swelling. The papule ulcerates and is infiltrated by neutrophils, lymphocytes, and plasma cells, followed by healing and regeneration of the epithelium (15).

In addition, genetic risk factors can determine individual susceptibility to recurrent aphthous stomatitis: in particular, several DNA polymorphisms of the NOD-like receptor 3 (NLRP3) (16), toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) (17), interleukin (IL)-6 (18), E-selectin (19), IL-1beta, and TNF-alpha genes (20). However, despite the large number of factors explored, the cause that triggers the episodes of ulcers has not been discovered. This means that clinically, the emergence of new lesions cannot be avoided.

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS

RAS is known to be extremely painful (12). These idiopathic ulcerations are oval lesions of different sizes with clean edges surrounded by an erythematous halo. At the center of the ulceration, the necrotic fundus is covered with a yellow-white fibrinous exudate (21). Ulcers typically present in the non-masticatory mucosa of the cheeks, lips, ventral and lateral surfaces of the tongue, non-attached gingiva, and occasionally, soft palate (15). RAS lesions are self-limiting (simple aphthosis), resolving within one or two weeks in most patients (22). In people affected by the disease, ulcers can compromise important functions such as nutrition, speech, oral hygiene (23), and quality of life (24). This is critical, considering that the lesions can last more than two weeks, with recurrent episodes in a period of between one and four months (8). RAS occurs in three morphological presentations: minor-type (Mikulicz ulcers, 2-10 mm in diameter), which is the most common (Figure 2); major aphthous (also called Sutton ulcers or peradenitis necrotic mucosa, >10 mm in diameter); and herpetiform ulceration (multiple small ulcers) (25). Some patients have continuous oral ulcerations; in these cases, some ulcers heal as others develop, with occasional genital ulcers. This

corresponds to a clinical state called complex aphthosis (8). Complex aphthosis has an underlying systemic cause, which does not correspond to RAS diagnosis.

Figure 2. Small ulcers of the RAS minor type (Mikulicz). They are very painful.

DISEASE PHASES

The sequence covers the stages of premonition (24 hours, with symptoms but no visible signs of disease), pre-ulcerative (18 hours up to 3 days, erythema and mild edema), ulcerative (varies greatly in the range of 1–16 days, active ulcer), healing (4–35 days, usually <21 days, decrease in symptoms and progressive healing), and remission (no evidence of ulcers) (26). The ulcerative and remission phases are those that we can evaluate with greater objectivity in the dental examination. Disease recurrence is established with the appearance of new ulcers. Disease severity can be determined based on the number, size, and location of the lesions; pain; duration; ulcer-free period (27); and impact on patient quality of life (24, 28).

MICROSCOPIC ASPECTS

The diagnosis of RAS is eminently clinical and is based on careful examination. Incisional or excisional biopsy of ulcers is recommended only in cases of uncertainty, when the presence of an oral disease producing ulcers or a malignancy is suspected (29). The microscopic characteristics of RAS are nonspecific. The pre-ulcerative lesion shows subepithelial inflammatory mononuclear cells with abundant mast cells, edema of the connective tissue, and neutrophils lining the margins. Damage to the epithelium usually begins in the basal layer and progresses through the superficial layers, ultimately leading to ulceration and surface exudation (2, 8).

EXPERIMENTAL MODELS

Until today, the only and best way to study this disease has been in patients who suffer from it. The English literature proposed two models for the experimental study of RAS, both

using rabbits. One of them induces ulcers with 50% acetic acid (30, 31) and the other by surgical incision in the oral mucosa (32). Neither registered molecules participating in the inflammatory processes described in RAS. Considering that RAS is an immunologically mediated disease, the chemical and mechanical induction of ulcers cannot be considered valid models.

TREATMENT

Therapeutic alternatives focus on reducing painful symptoms (33). In the clinic today, dental surgeons can offer the promise that the ulcers will probably heal in two weeks, and in more complex cases, a therapy based on topical corticosteroids (34), which is the same approach used for several diseases of unknown cause (such as pemphigus, pemphigoid, and oral lichen planus). Despite the use of topical corticosteroids over several years for RAS, there is a lack of high-quality evidence of their efficacy (35) and even less for systemic interventions (28). However, the recommended option is the combination of a topical corticosteroid plus a topical anesthetic and a buccal antiseptic (36). The combination includes triamcinolone (0.1% paste, up to four times daily) in addition to topical lidocaine (2% viscous solution, maximum 8 doses/day) and as an adjuvant, oropharyngeal chlorhexidine (0.12%, 15 mL as a mouthwash twice daily) (4). Patients should be instructed to avoid recognized trigger foods, and acidic foods and drinks (37).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Taking into account the key concepts associated with RAS (Table 1), biomedical research has several questions to answer, such as 1) what is the molecular difference between a healthy patient and a sick patient? 2) which are the molecules of an ulcerative phase and a phase of remission of the disease? and 3) are there molecules that can predict the clinical

course and the severity of ulcers? Answering these questions can open up new therapeutic and preventive possibilities.

FUNDING

Fondecyt 11180170 funds this article.

COMPETING INTERESTS

There are no conflicts of interest.

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